

Editorial

Blends, composites, biocomposites and nanocomposites

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The field of bio/natural polymers has shown enormous growth over the past several decades in terms of both scientific advancements and technological developments (1). This issue of AICM covers the selected abstracts of papers presented at the First International Online Conference on Blends, Composites, Bio-Composites and Nanocomposites (ICNC-2020) held during 9 – 11, October 2020 at Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala, India (2). I am very glad that AICM is rapidly achieving our mission by acting as an advanced educational platform for sharing the most recent research data in the form of abstracts. This platform is very helpful for researchers, especially during this pandemic period, as most of the conferences and meetings taking place in an online mode where the traditional way of abstract sharing does not work.

It is noteworthy to mention that ICNC-2020 brought together scientists, technologists, and other experts to share their knowledge on recent developments in the field of bio or natural polymers, and their blends, composites, biomaterials, hydrogels, IPNs from macro to nano scales. The conference was very useful in the sense that it was attended by hundreds of chemists, physicists, biologists, technologists, doctors and engineers, making it a truly interdisciplinary conference. Some of the selected abstracts of this issue cover a brief discussion on natural rubber nanocomposites with nanofillers like cellulose nanofibers. Such discussions provided useful information on the importance of latex mixing for developing rubber nanocomposites and the effects of cellulose fiber morphology and modification on the features of blends. Some other authors discussed the development of natural polymer (E.g., carboxymethylcellulose) based membranes for the separation of various substances from industrial mixtures. Development of water/oil/water multiple emulsions for the co-delivery of lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs with improved oral pharmacokinetics is another interesting research that is included with this issue. A study that reports the *in vitro* and *in vivo* evaluation of solid lipid nanoparticles of paclitaxel and cisplatin delivery for ovarian cancer treatment also seems very interesting. The applications of dendrimers in a variety of fields such as drug delivery, gene delivery, imaging, diagnosis, and photodynamic therapy have also been discussed. Another interesting study shows the applicability of biochar as filler in polyester composites.

We hope that this issue will help to foster the advancement of scientific research on these topics and result in worthwhile discussions.

Keywords: *Natural polymers, Blends, Composites, Natural Polymers, Biomaterials*

References

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